

Procurement Process as a Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria

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Abstract: The study investigates "Procurement Process as a Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria. The aim of the research is to explore the effectiveness of procurement processes as a Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria. The study employed quantitative method approach by using data from survey in the Nigerian procurement landscape. A sample size of 110 procurement stakeholders from whom data were obtained using online structured survey questions. The collected data were analyzed using ANOVA with SPSS to test research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results show significance between dependent and independent variable tested hence the two formulated null hypotheses were rejected, while their corresponding alternative hypotheses were accepted, confirming significance between the variables. The study made the following findings: there is significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria; and there is significant relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria. The research objectives 1, and of the study were achieved and the empirical findings indicate that a transparent, accountable, and well-regulated procurement process can play a critical role in addressing corruption in Nigeria. Recommendation includes: adoption and implantation of mandatory e-procurement systems across all government agencies to minimize human intervention and reduce opportunities for corruption across Nigeria. The study made significant contributions to the global repository of knowledge by providing actionable policy recommendations for policymakers and public officials in Nigeria. The outcome of this study will be beneficial to citizens, government, policy makers and other procurement stakeholders across Nigeria.

Keywords: *Quantitative, Hypotheses, Independent variable, ANOVA, Opportunities*

1. Introduction

The issue of corruption in Nigeria's public procurement system has been a persistent challenge, significantly impeding the country's economic growth and development. Public procurement, as a major avenue for government spending, is susceptible to corrupt practices due to the large financial transactions and the involvement of multiple stakeholders, (Basheka, 2021). This research proposal aims to explore the potential of reforming procurement processes as a strategic approach to combat corruption in Nigeria.

According to Okeke-Ogbuafor, and Gray, (2021), the term "Panacea" comes from Greek mythology, where the goddess Panacea was associated with all-purpose healing. Nowadays, it's used to describe a treatment or solution that may address any issue or challenge, frequently within a certain setting (Okeke-Ogbuafor & Gray, 2021). It is typically used in a metaphorical way to refer to a single solution that is anticipated to address a complicated problem with many facets.

Public procurement in Nigeria accounts for a substantial portion of the national budget, making it a critical sector for economic and infrastructural development, (Maduekeh et al., 2022). However, the procurement process has been plagued by various forms of corruption,

including bribery, nepotism, and embezzlement. According to Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index, Nigeria has consistently ranked poorly, indicating a severe corruption problem (Nwogbo & Ighodalo, 2021). This endemic corruption undermines the efficiency of public spending and deters foreign investment, which is crucial for economic development (Amoh et al., 2022).

Historically, Nigeria's procurement system has been characterized by a lack of transparency and accountability (Abioro, 2021). The Public Procurement Act of 2007 was a significant step towards reforming procurement processes, aiming to establish a more transparent, competitive, and fair system (Panya & Awuor, 2023). Despite this legislation, implementation has been inconsistent, and corrupt practices continue to pervade procurement activities (Onyango, 2022).

The impact of corruption in procurement extends beyond financial losses (Fazekas et al., 2022). It has substantial social implications, including the erosion of public trust in government institutions and the hindrance of socio-economic development. When funds intended for public services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure are misappropriated, the quality of these services

deteriorates, disproportionately affecting the most vulnerable populations, (Basavarajappa, 2020). Internationally, several countries have successfully implemented procurement reforms to curb corruption, (Križić, 2021). For instance, Georgia and Rwanda have significantly improved their procurement systems through comprehensive reforms, including digitalization and strict enforcement of procurement laws, (Amankwa & Tetteh, 2022). These examples provide valuable insights into potential strategies that could be adapted and implemented in the Nigerian context.

Reforming Nigeria's public procurement processes presents a viable strategy to tackle the pervasive issue of corruption. By learning from global best practices and understanding the unique challenges within Nigeria, this research aims to contribute to the development of effective procurement models that promote transparency, accountability, and efficiency, fostering economic growth and social development.

The procurement process has been plagued by various forms of corruption, including bribery, nepotism, and embezzlement (Obicci, 2024). Despite various anti-corruption initiatives, Nigeria continues to struggle with prominent levels of corruption, especially in its

procurement systems, (Aduwo et al., 2020). The inadequacy of current measures to address this endemic issue calls for a thorough examination of procurement processes as a potential solution. This study aims to identify the gaps in the existing procurement framework that facilitate corrupt practices and to propose effective strategies to mitigate these issues. The aim of this research is to explore the effectiveness of procurement processes as a Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: to analyze the current procurement practices in Nigeria and identify key areas prone to corruption; and to assess the impact of corruption in procurement on Nigeria's socio-economic development. The study will provide a comprehensive understanding of the role of procurement processes in curbing corruption. By identifying the weaknesses in the current system and suggesting practical solutions, it can guide policymakers in reforming procurement practices. The findings could significantly contribute to enhancing transparency, accountability, and efficiency in public spending, thereby fostering economic development in Nigeria.

1.1 Research Questions

- i.**What is the relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria?

ii. What is the impact of corruption in procurement on Nigeria's socio-economic development?

1.2 Hypotheses

Two research hypotheses were developed as stated below:

H0₁: there is no significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria.

H0₂: there is no significant relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Corruption in Procurement

Corruption in public procurement is a pervasive challenge that undermines governance, hampers economic development, and erodes public trust across the globe. As defined by the World Bank (1997), and cited by Fagbadebo, and Mbada, (2021), public procurement corruption entails any illegitimate use of public office for private gain during the procurement process. This multifaceted issue distorts market operations, inhibits fair competition, and leads to suboptimal public service outcomes, severely impacting infrastructure quality and delivery, (Soemartono & Sriwijaya, 2024). The implications of such corruption are global,

affecting both developed and developing nations, albeit with varying degrees of severity and manifestation. However, in countries like Nigeria, where corruption is deeply entrenched within the socio-political fabric, the repercussions are particularly profound, significantly impeding national development efforts (Chinweuba, 2020).

Nigeria, despite its status as one of Africa's largest economies and most populous nations, has long grappled with the challenges posed by corruption, especially within its public procurement sector, (Buhar & Momoh, (2021). The sector is critically vulnerable, being a major avenue for corrupt practices including but not limited to bid rigging, kickbacks, and the embezzlement of public funds (Buhar & Momoh, 2021). These practices not only undermine the integrity and efficiency of public spending but also contribute to the broader issues of poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment in the country (Ikenga & Chima, 2021).

Addressing procurement corruption is paramount for improving governance, ensuring economic progress, and promoting social equity (Basheka, 2021). An effective public procurement system is vital for the judicious use of public funds, ensuring that they serve their intended purpose in delivering value for

money in public services and infrastructure projects, (Matto et al., 2021). Moreover, tackling this issue head-on is critical for fostering a more transparent, accountable, and fair society, (Matto, et al., 2021).

This literature review aims to dissect the multifaceted nature of procurement corruption, with a special focus on Nigeria. It outlines the significance of the topic, explores its global implications, and delves into the specific challenges and opportunities within the Nigerian context. By weaving together theoretical frameworks, empirical studies, and successful global case studies, this review sets the stage for a nuanced understanding of procurement corruption and paves the way for identifying effective strategies to combat it in Nigeria and beyond. The relationship between procurement processes and corruption is a complex interplay of organizational, psychological, and socio-political factors, (Harnois & Gagnon, (2022). Performance-Based Evaluation Criteria (PBEC) in Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) highlight the discretion of the purchaser as a significant point of influence, where corruption and accountability dynamics can substantially affect procurement outcomes, (Cao & Wang, 2023). This perspective underscores the necessity of establishing robust frameworks that minimize discretion or subjectivity in

procurement decisions, aiming to reduce corruption's foothold.

Understanding the dynamics of procurement corruption requires delving into various theoretical frameworks that offer insights into the causes, mechanisms, and possible mitigation strategies for corruption in procurement processes, (Khan & Krishnan, 2021). Among these, organizational theories provide a foundational perspective, offering explanations for the occurrence of corruption within the interactions between governments and contractors, and how institutional environments shape organizational behaviors towards corruption, (Sartor & Beamish2020). Public procurement has evolved from a basic administrative function into a critical element in public service delivery, significantly impacting economic and social development, (Sönnichsen & Clement, 2020). In Nigeria, the introduction of the Public Procurement Act (PPA) in 2007 marked a significant milestone aimed at regulating and improving the procurement processes, which were previously plagued by corruption and inefficiency, (Mendoza & Cruz, 2020). This literature review examines the effectiveness of the procurement process in combating corruption in Nigeria, drawing on various studies and reports.

2.2 Organizational Theories

One of the cornerstone theories in understanding procurement corruption is the principal-Agent Theory, (Smith, 2022). This theory examines the relationship between principals (governments) and agents (contractors), where the principal delegates work to the agent. A key issue arising in this relationship is information asymmetry, where the agent has more information than the principal, (Vosooghidizaji et al., 2020). This asymmetry can create opportunities for the agent to act in self-interest rather than in the best interest of the principal, potentially leading to corrupt practices such as bribery, nepotism, and fraud. Jensen and Meckling's seminal work (1976) on agency problems and the theory of the firm elaborates on how such informational discrepancies can lead to agency costs and how various mechanisms can be designed to align the interests of the agent with those of the principal, thus reducing the scope for corruption, (Vian, 2020).

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Materials

The following Hardware and software were used for the study: computer set; printer and rim of a4 paper; pen; field note; electricity; internet services (internet router and data

Another important perspective is offered by Institutional Theory, which focuses on the broader context in which organizations operate. This theory posits that the institutional environment – comprising norms, regulations, and cultural expectations – plays a significant role in shaping organizational behavior. According to Crossley et al. (2021), organizations tend to conform to the expectations of their institutional environment to gain legitimacy, access resources, and ensure survival. In contexts where corruption is pervasive, this conformity pressure can lead organizations to engage in or tolerate corrupt practices as a means to adapt and thrive within their institutional contexts, (Al-Qudah, 2024). Thus, Institutional Theory highlights the importance of systemic reforms in the institutional environment to combat procurement corruption effectively (Al-Qudah, 2024).

3.2 Method

The study employed a quantitative research approach to methodically investigate “Procurement Process as A Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria”.

3.3 Population

Procurement officials, and other pertinent stakeholders involved in public procurement of selected government organization in Nigeria make up the population for this study who are employees across Nigeria, who are actively engaged in procurement activities. The population for the study was decided using the opinions of Ebabu, Tsunekawa, Haregeweyn, Tsubo, Adgo, Fenta, and Poesen, (2022). who carried a similar study and recommended the use of procurement stakeholders' personnel as respondents. The study populations of 150 procurement stakeholder professionals were chosen from whom the respondents were drawn using the formula proposed by Yamane in 1967, and cited by Kiarie (2020), to arrive at the sample size. The selection formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2} \quad [1]$$

Where $n \rightarrow$ the required sample size

$N =$ is the Target Population (150 employees)

$e =$ accuracy level required. Standard error = 5%

Sample calculation

$$n = 150 / (1 + 150 (0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 150 / 1.375$$

$$n = 109.9$$

$$n = 110 \text{ Respondents}$$

Therefore, minimum of 110 respondents are required for this study

The sampling population for this study is 110 respondents who are procurement specialists/professionals and other pertinent stakeholders involved in procurement in public institutions. The sample size was chosen applying the views of Mwangi, (2020) as guide. Random sampling was employed for the study. Random sampling was employed in the study. Random sampling frequently minimizes the sampling error in the population, as it minimizes human biases in sampling, (Legg, & Moon, 2020).

3.4 Data Collection

Quantitative data collection approach was employed for the study using the views of Rahman, (2020). The study collected primary data using a structured questionnaire that was designed based on relevant literature, research question, objective of the study and theoretical frameworks to gather needed data from the participants. An online survey was distributed to respondents who were randomly selected. Questionnaire used for the study composed of open and closed ended questions which agrees with the views of Kiarie (2020). The closed-ended questions were to gauge various aspects including the impact of stakeholder relationship on procurement of public work contracts in public tertiary institution in south-east, Nigeria.

3.5 Data Analysis

Quantitative data generated through the survey were collated, coded and analyzed using Analysis of Variance, (ANOVA) With Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 23.

3.6 Decision Rule for Hypotheses Testing

According to Zhang, (2022), at a given level of significance, If the p-value obtained is lower than 0.05, it indicates that the relationship between the variables is statistically significant, hence reject the null hypothesis (H_0) while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. Conversely, p-value (>0.05) indicates that the relationship between the variables is not statistically significant, hence accept the null hypothesis (H_0) while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) should be rejected, (Pandey & Pandey, 2021).

4.0 Result and Discussion

This section presents details, analysis, interpretation of the data collected from the field and discussion to gain good insight on the subject matter being investigated. The data presentation is in two parts. The first part which is presented in section 4.1; is the background information of the respondents. While, the second part being the main research questions is organized according to the specific objectives of the study and presented in section

4.2. The 110 copies of research instrument distributed were all valid for the analysis and in useable form.

4.1 Gender distribution of Respondent

Figure 4.2: Gender Distribution of Respondents
Field Survey (2024)

Figure 4.2. presents the gender distribution of respondents. A total of 109 responses were received, out of which 78 (71.6%) of respondents are males while 31 (28.4%) are females, indicating that more of the respondents are males.

4.2. Age of Distribution of Respondent

109 Responses

Figure 4.3: Age Distribution of Respondents
Field Survey (2024)

Figure 4.3 presents age distribution of respondents. 1 (0.9%) of the respondents are between the ages of 30-35; 24 (22%) are within the ages of 36-40; 30(27.5%) are within the

ages of 31-45; 19 (17.4%) are within the ages of 45-50; while 15 (13.8%) are within the ages of the remaining above 50. The average of sampled respondents is 33 years, indicating that most of the respondents are young people who in the prime of their careers and capable of contributing meaningfully to their respective organizations. This indicates that the respondents gave accurate and sufficient information and were old enough to comprehend the main points of the study. It is implied that the data produced were error-free and served as a solid foundation for the analysis, interpretation, and final recommendations.

4.3. Number of years working in the organization

Figure 4.4: Years of years working in their organization. Field Survey (2024)

Figure 4.4. presents summarized data on respondents’ years of experience in their organization. The survey further shows that 23 (21.1%) of the respondents have over 20 years of experience in their current organization; 45

(41.3%) have between 11 to 24 years of procurement experience; while the remaining 40 (37.3%) have 0 to 10 years of procurement experience; This is an indication that more of the respondents have, middle level of experience in their respective current organization which is good enough to contribute meaningfully to the survey. Accordingly, these workers or responders have extensive knowledge of what transpires in their workplaces. This suggested that by using this type of work experience, it was possible to extract information for the study that would not have been possible to obtain by using different groups.

4.5. Educational qualifications of Respondents

Figure 4.5: Educational Qualifications of Respondents. Field Survey (2024)

Figure 4.5 presents educational qualifications of respondents. Educational backgrounds of the respondents, according to the survey, indicates that 4 (3.7%) are PhD. Holders; 40 (36.79%)

are M. Sc. holders; 44 (40.4%) are B. Sc holders; 8 (7.3%) are OND and HND holders; while 13 (11.9%) hold other qualifications. This also indicates that a greater percentage of the respondents are educated enough to contribute meaningfully to the survey. The

inference is that the data provided by the respondents was reliable, accurate, and valid for making conclusions about how procurement practices can be used to control corruption.

Table 4.1: Relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria.

H01: there is no significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria.										
Question	SD	D	N	A	SA	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Decision
I am familiar with the current procurement practices in Nigeria.	0	2	10	56	41	108	2.03	0.54	0.03	Reject Ho1
2. The most common forms of corruption I have observed in procurement processes in Nigeria are evident.	0	8	9	62	30	108	2.06	0.61	0.04	Reject Ho1
3. Certain stages of the procurement process are more vulnerable to corruption than others.	0	9	10	55	35	108	2.05	0.59	0.04	Reject Ho1

Source: Field study 2024

The two research hypotheses which were developed from research questions 1 and 2; research objectives 1 and 2 were tested using ANOVA with SPSS version 22. The values assigned to Likert scale are as follows: 5 = strongly agreed (SA); 4 = agreed (A); 3 = Neutral (N); 2 = disagreed (D); and 1 =

strongly disagreed (SD), were adopted from the work of Robinson, (2024).

NOVA was employed on SPSS to analyze the quantitative data presented in Table 4.1 and used for testing research hypothesis (H0₁) at 0.05 level of significance. However, H0₁ was derived using data obtained from survey questions 1; 2; and 3. The following P-values

0.03; 0.04; 0.04 for survey questions 1; 2; and 3 respectively, at 95% confidence interval (0.05 level of significance).

Each of the obtained P-values 0.03; 0.04; 0.04 at 0.05 level of significance is lower than 0.05 (95% confidence interval of the difference), which indicates that there is a significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria. Hence also by applying the decision rule stated earlier in section 3.6, the null hypothesis (H_0) is which states that “there is no significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria.” is therefore rejected. while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which states that “there is significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria” is hereby accepted. This implies that there is significant relationship between procurement processes and corruption in Nigeria.

The result obtained here is similar to that of Kohler, and Dimancesco, (2020), who found that “One of the government operations most susceptible to corruption in Nigeria is public procurement. According to the research, Nigerian procurement procedures frequently lack openness, which fuels pervasive corruption. It was discovered that non-competitive bidding, restricted access to

procurement information, and opaque bidding procedures were the main causes of fraudulent behaviors in the procurement industry.

Similarly, the result is in tandem with the reports from the Economic and Financial crime Commission in (2018), cited by Nabiebu, Otu, and Alobu, (2023), who opined that procurement procedures are connected to a sizable percentage of corruption cases in Nigeria,. In order to influence contract results, bribes and kickbacks are frequently transferred throughout the contract award phase, according to the EFCC. The commission emphasized that in order to combat corruption, procurement laws must be strictly enforced to prevent, detect and prosecute offender with associated assets of the culprits confiscated.

Meanwhile, previous empirical researches have repeatedly demonstrated a substantial relationship between high levels of corruption in Nigeria and ineffective procurement procedures. The main conclusions here highlight the significance of adopting e-procurement technologies, enforcing procurement laws, developing the capacity of procurement authorities, and maintaining openness and integrity in institutional frameworks. These steps are crucial for lowering corruption and enhancing the effectiveness and integrity of Nigeria's procurement procedures.

Table 4.2: Relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria.

H0₂: there is no significant relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria										
Question	SD	D	N	A	SA	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
4. Corruption in procurement significantly impacts the quality of public services in Nigeria.	7	6	7	35	54	108	2.02	0.31	0.01	Reject H ₀₂
5. Procurement corruption has adversely affected infrastructure development in Nigeria.	1	10	9	46	43	108	2.02	0.25	0.01	Reject H ₀₂
6. Socio-economic sectors in Nigeria are severely affected by procurement corruption.	1	10	9	49	40	108	2.03	0.49	0.02	Reject H ₀₂
Procurement corruption negatively influences foreign investment in Nigeria.	0	3	22	55	29	108	2.03	0.26	0.01	Reject H ₀₂

Similarly, ANOVA was employed on SPSS to analyze the quantitative data presented in Table 4.2 and used for testing research hypothesis (H₀₂) at 0.05 level of significance. However, H₀₂ was derived using data obtained from survey questions 4; 5; 6; and 7. The following P-values 0.01; 0.01; 0.02 and 0.01 for survey questions 4; 5; 6; and 7 respectively, at 95% confidence interval (0.05 level of significance).

Each of the obtained P-values 0.01; 0.01; 0.02 and 0.01 at 0.05 level of significance is lower than 0.05 (95% confidence interval of the difference), which indicates that there is a significant relationship between corruption in

procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria. Hence also by applying the decision rule stated earlier in section 3.6, the null hypothesis (H₀₂) is which states that “there is no significant relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria” is therefore rejected. while the alternative hypothesis (H₂) which states that “there is significant relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria” is hereby accepted. This implies that there is significant relationship between corruption in procurement and socio-economic development in Nigeria.

This result is not different from that obtained from that of the World Bank in 2016, who carried out an extensive investigation on the effects of procurement corruption on Nigeria's socioeconomic advancement, (Aduwo et al., 2020). The study found that substantial financial losses resulting from procurement process corruption impede the nation's socioeconomic progress. The research emphasized that money intended for the development of healthcare, education, and infrastructure is frequently diverted through dishonest procurement methods, which stunts economic progress and leaves the public with subpar services, (Aduwo et al., 2020).

According to Dimuna, (2023), Transparency International did research in 2020, in which they looked at the connection between Nigeria's socioeconomic progress and procurement corruption. According to the report, procurement corruption raises project prices and results in poor project execution, both of which have a long-term detrimental impact on economic development and progress. To promote socioeconomic growth, TI suggested implementing strict anti-corruption measures in procurement procedures.

An extensive negative correlation has been shown by previous empirical research to exist

between Nigeria's socioeconomic progress and procurement corruption. Results from several studies have consistently demonstrated that corruption in public procurement results in monetary losses, wasteful public expenditure, poor quality infrastructure and public services, a rise in poverty and inequality, and a slower rate of economic expansion. Therefore, improved accountability and transparency in procurement procedures, strong supervision systems, and the implementation of anti-corruption measures are all necessary to achieve socio-economic growth.

4. Conclusions

The research on "Procurement Process as a Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria" offers a thorough examination of the ways in which efficient procurement procedures might reduce corrupt behaviors. Undermining public trust, economic progress, and the general efficiency of government operations, corruption is still a major problem in Nigeria. The research objectives 1, to 2 of the study were achieved and the empirical findings indicate that a transparent, accountable, and well-regulated procurement process can play a critical role in addressing corruption in Nigeria. The following conclusions were made:

- i.that implementing transparent procurement processes ensures that all stages of procurement are open to scrutiny in Nigeria;

ii. that training and capacity building of procurement authorities and other stakeholders, is essential to the successful execution of procurement rules in Nigeria;

iii. that integrating cutting-edge technology, like blockchain, can produce an unchangeable transaction record, making it more difficult for dishonest behavior to go undetected in Nigeria.

Based on the findings of the study on

“Procurement Process as A Panacea for Corruption in Nigeria” the authors were propose five important recommendations as follows:

- i. The Public Procurement Act of 2007 should be updated and amended to reflect contemporary issues and global best practices.
- ii. Enactment of laws requiring mandatory publication of all procurement-related information, such as contract awards, evaluation standards, and bid submissions all over Nigeria.
- iii. Adoption and implantation of mandatory e-procurement systems across all government agencies to minimize human intervention and reduce opportunities for corruption across Nigeria.
- iv. Provision of continuous training and capacity-building programs for all public procurement officials to ensure they are knowledgeable about best practices and ethical standards across Nigeria.
- v. Establishment of independent units dedicated to auditing public procurement procedures in order

to find opportunities for improvement on a regular basis across Nigeria.

Conclusively, has made several significant contributions to the global repository of knowledge by advocating a holistic approach to the fight corruption in procurement, recognizing that reform alone is not a panacea but must be part of a broader strategy that includes political will, societal change, and continuous monitoring in Nigeria. This comprehensive perspective contributes to the broader field of anti-corruption studies.

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